

THE IMPORTANCE OF PERSONAL MOTIVES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PROFESSIONAL IMAGE IN THE STUDENTS OF PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article highlights the importance of personal motives in the development of professional image of students of professional education. The concept of image and world experience in the development of professional image was studied and analyzed. In conducting the research, V. Gerbachevsky's questionnaire (personal motivation) and N. Pryajnikov's "Methodology for activating students' career orientation" were used. analysis of the obtained results is described.*

Keywords: *image, professional image, professional self-awareness, motive, motivation, personal motivation, professional development.*

Introduction.

PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", PF-5847 of October 8, 2019 "The Supreme the concept of development of the education system until 2030" Decrees, Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 No. PQ-4884 "On additional measures to further improve the education system", Professional it is important to theoretically-practically solve the priority tasks defined in other normative legal documents related to educational activities from a socio-psychological point of view.

Image research is carried out by the world's leading higher education institutions and scientific centers, in particular, Stanford University (USA), Loughborough University (UK), Leipzig Institute of Applied Sciences (Germany), Copenhagen University (Denmark), International Institute of Pedagogical Sciences (China), Seoul National University (South Korea), Russian Academy of Iconology (Russian Federation).

The main part.

Relevance of the topic. As a result of the extremely high level of overcrowding of various higher education institutions, in the modern conditions of the educational market, secondary vocational education faces a number of urgent problems: increasing the competitiveness of these professional education services and improving their systematic operation, and it is important to expand the network of secondary vocational education institutions, to include educated young people in them. The success of solving the identified problems depends on the effectiveness of forming a positive image of students in professional education. Thus, the relevance of the scientific article is determined by the lack of a systematic analysis of the image of professional education students in psychology.

A brief analysis of scientific research on the topic. Various problems that arise in the social and psychological factors of image formation from the scientists of Uzbekistan R.Z.Gainutdinov, M.G.Davletshin, A.M.Jabborov, A.A.Zokirov, V.M.Karimova, Z.T.Nishonova, A.I.Rasulov, G'.B.Shoumarov , Kadyrov, E.G'. Goziev, Sh.A. Eshmetov and others were scientifically

researched. However, the features of image formation of professional education students have not been studied as a separate social-psychological problem.

S.A. Azarenko, Ye.N. Bogdanov, Ye.V. Gordienko, V.G. Gorchakova, A.A. Derkach, A.S. Kovalchuk, Ye.I. Manyakina, A.Yu. Panasyuk from scientists of the Commonwealth of Independent States. Although Ye.B. Pereligina, G.G. Pocheptsov, A.V. Sokolov, V.M. Shepel, I.P. Shkuratova and others carried out research on personal image, representation of external appearance in the image, characteristics of individual image formation, professional image of professional education students socio-psychological factors affecting development have not been studied as a complex socio-psychological study.

Researches of foreign researchers C. Atkin, M.E. Blo, D.M. Bus, K. Boulding, A. Clark, A.P. Eagly, B.T. Johnson, M. Elwood, E. Klinger, E. Krechmer, L.C. Winters and others in advertising, marketing and organizational image formation implemented within the framework of issues.

Scientific novelty of the article.

In the development of professional image among students of professional education, the results were analyzed and proven based on self-assessment and direct compliance with the norm.

The importance of personal motivation in the formation of a professional image has been proven by analyzing students' motives such as internal motive, competition motive, defeat avoidance motive, self-respect, and will power.

The purpose of the study is to study the psychological factors of professional image development among students of professional educational institution as the object of research, Termiz Law Technical College (60 students), Termiz Abu Ali Ibn Sina Technical College of Public Health (60 students). 120 respondents consisting of students were involved.

The empirical source of the research was the methodology and results of questionnaires. The communicative and management function of the image is especially active in the post-industrial era.

A person's hard work will have additional value. As a result, a person is an expert in his field and begins to work on creating a positive image of his profession. Image is the identity of the choice of goods and services in a competitive environment. A good positive image is the main criterion for the success of a person or the effective development of an organization.

In modern socio-economic and socio-cultural conditions, the importance of the image often corresponds to the external characteristics of its bearer and, at first glance, is not scientifically related to the object and subject.

However, it cannot be denied that there is a detailed practice of forming personal, corporate, political and other types of images that indicate the existence of this phenomenon, and therefore there is a need for a scientific review. In the development of the image of students of professional education, the motives and self-esteem of a person, i.e., how well they can perform labor actions, are also important.

Analyzing the results of our research, the majority of students highly rated the work they could do. Overestimating themselves means that they are ready to overcome all difficulties in their chosen profession.

We obtained the following results from our research on the formation of personal motivation.

Figure 1. Results of the method of activating students' career guidance.
1) Termiz law college 2) Termiz public care college
a) Underestimate b) standard estimate c) overestimate

1) Innate motive 2) cognitive motive 3) avoiding failure motive 4) competition motive 5) career exchange motive 6) self – respect motive 7) difficult task motive 8) stamina 9) achievements 10) self – esteem 11) using own power 12) potential results 13) results 14) activeness
a) Termiz law college b) Termiz public care college

Figure 2. Analysis of the results of the methodology of personal motivation.

As can be seen from these results, we can see that in most of the respondents, the motive of knowledge, the motive of competition, the motive of self-respect, and the initiative motive prevail. Professionals in both fields are motivated to overcome difficulties in their chosen fields. Based on these results, it can be said that the owner of a correctly chosen profession based on the motive can be in the image that is most suitable for him. It can be explained by the fact that during the acquisition of professional activity and professional activity, he creates his image based on professional requirements and experiences professional adaptation faster.

CONCLUSION

The research carried out on the socio-psychological characteristics of the image of students of professional education made it possible to come to the following conclusions:

1. In the study of socio-psychological factors of the formation of the image of students of professional education, the situation of the phenomenon of image being studied in the sciences of linguistics, political science, sociology, philosophy, marketing and pedagogy served as a methodological basis.

2. In the development of the image of students of professional education, the self-evaluation of motives and a person is very important. The extent to which he is able to perform labor activities indicates his interest in his profession.

3. In the development of the image of students of professional education, we can see the dominance of the motive of knowledge, the motive of competition, the motive of self-respect, initiative. It can be explained by the fact that he creates his own image based on the acquisition of professional activity and professional requirements, and experiences professional adaptation faster.

4. In the research, it was found that personal motives and career orientation are important factors in creating and describing the image of students of professional education.

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